

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

МЕТАФОРИЧЕСКОЕ И ЛИНГВОКОНИТИВНОЕ ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗООМОРФИЗМА, ОТНОСЯЩЕГОСЯ К КОНКРЕТНОМУ ЧЕЛОВЕКУ, В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИЯХ ИСКУССТВА

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METAPHORICAL AND LINGVOCOGNITIVE FORMATION OF ZOOMORPHISM RELATED TO A SPECIFIC PERSON IN WORKS OF ART

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Аннотация

В данной статье представлено использование зооморфизмов в произведениях искусства и их анализ, а также метафорическое образование зооморфизмов, относящихся к конкретному человеку. Кроме того, излагаются теоретические мнения лингвистов о зооморфизмах, использовании кличек домашних животных в разных ситуациях и в разных значениях, приводятся и подробно анализируются примеры словосочетаний, связанных с названиями животных.

Abstract

This article presents the use of zoomorphisms in works of art and their analysis, as well as the metaphorical formation of zoomorphisms related to a specific person. Moreover, the theoretical opinions of linguists about zoomorphisms, the use of pet names in different situations and in different meanings are expressed, and examples of phrases related to animal names are given and analyzed in detail.

Ключевые слова. Произведение искусства, зооморфизм, метафора, языковой феномен, этнокультурный зооморфизм, дикое животное.

Keywords: Work of art, zoomorphism, metaphor, linguistic phenomenon, ethnocultural zoomorphism, wild animal.

INTRODUCTION. In recent years, despite the fact that sufficient research has been conducted on metaphor in world linguistics, the interest in it is increasing day by day. Because in order to use the words in the language, there is a need to know their figurative meanings as well as their own meaning. This creates the need for a comprehensive study of metaphor in linguistics. Accordingly, as a result of many studies, the basic rules related to the use of metaphor in oral and literary style were developed and the concept of metaphor was defined as a language unit. Because metaphor, as a linguistic phenomenon, accompanies language and speech everywhere, and from this point of view, many linguists consider metaphor from different perspectives and express their opinions about this phenomenon. In many fiction books, zoomorphic images are formed using metaphors. Zoomorphism refers to the metaphorical use of animal images in forming a figurative description of a person or object.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT. We should pay special attention to the opinions of A.P. Chudinov, a linguist. According to him, metaphor should be interpreted as a basic mental process that unites two conceptual field and allows us to use the power of constructing a source field using a new field. These points of view also affect the study of metaphors in Uzbek linguistics. Due to their linguistic properties, zoomorphisms provide rich and interesting material for researching the problem of the reflection of

human life or, in other words, the worldview in language. According to F. Guketlova, the most convenient way to determine the ethnocultural specificity of the zoonymic lexicon describing a person is the traditional term "zoomorphism", which is understood as a metaphorical name manifested in the image of a specific representative of the fauna in the analysis of the lexicon from the point of view of the emotional-evaluative description of a person.

Kiong, a linguist, studied zoomorphisms from the system-structural aspect. V. Kamenskaya and S. Ogdonova used zoonym and zoomorphism as synonyms for each other in their first studies, and later approved the terms zoocharacteristics and zoomorphism in relation to metaphor, and showed zoomorphisms as language units that create metaphorical meaning. O. Latipov's scientific research in Uzbek linguistics is devoted to the analysis of the semantic structure of pet names in Russian, Uzbek and Tajik languages. B. Zaripov conducted his scientific research on the role of zoonyms used in Navoi's works in the creation of artistic forms. G. Hakimova studied the structural-semantic aspect of phraseological units with zoonym component in the English language [1]. However, despite so many scientific studies, in linguistics, terms related to the animal world are called by different names, and their terminology has not been unified in terms of content and scope.

METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH.

One can imagine concepts in fiction where zoomorphism encourages people to imagine themselves as non-human animals. It can also be defined as art that depicts one type of animal as another animal species, or art that uses animals as a visual motive. Basically, the concept of zoomorphism refers to the use of animal names and characteristics in fiction in terms of human characters, and the description of animals in terms of certain traits and characteristics. This lexicological term is derived from the Greek language, meaning “zoo” - animal, “morphism” - form.

Emphasis was placed on the specifics of the reference to the human image through zoomorphisms, and mainly some animal names were used to reveal the human image and character traits. From the time when the primitive system and its worldview were formed, mankind has been interested and afraid of the world of nature and order. According to totemistic relations, lions, tigers, leopard, falcons, eagles, hawks are depicted as symbols of bravery, boldness, and nobility, while black ravens are depicted as symbols of meanness, blood-thirstiness. Language has several possibilities in revealing the human image through them. The importance of the vocabulary in the language increases even more when reflecting the image of a person through the images of animals and revealing their characters. Language has several possibilities in revealing the human image through them. The importance of the vocabulary in the language increases even more when reflecting the image of a person through the images of animals and revealing their characters. Since ancient times, people have had a very close relationship with animals and other animals in nature. The main goals of this were that animals have been the main helpers in everyday life and work for mankind for several thousand years. In addition, the animal world is the main source of food for mankind. Since the beginning of the development of consciousness in mankind, animals have been the main assistants in the process of hunting. This process caused people to fully master the secrets of the animal world, develop their work ability and increase their interest. As the skills of how to deal with wild animals are formed, the need to train domestic animals has always increased.

In many examples of fiction literature, the impressiveness of the style has led to the use of many animal characters and their names in order to expand the weight of the subjects and attract the reader's attention. For example, people who are cunning, deceitful and liars are depicted foxes, and stupid, greedy, and avaricious people are depicted wolves, and people who live in a carefree life only in pleasure and laughter are depicted to bear-like characteristics and names. Based on this, it can be said that each of these animal forms performed a specific methodological task in the text of the work. It should be noted that people with negative behavior and character are always depicted as beasts and wild animals, while people with positive and virtuous qualities are always depicted as domestic animals. We can find these ideas in the tales and epics of many Uzbek and world nations.

In fiction literature and art, animal characteristics can be depicted based on human behavior and character traits. It is known from history that in ancient countries, some gods were depicted in the form of animals, such views were considered an important factor not only in art, but also in the emergence of religious zoomorphism. Based on the mentality of its culture and history, each nation approaches animals with different beliefs and viewpoints. For example, historically, in the ancient Egyptian state, the god Anubis is usually depicted as a half-man and half-jackal, and in some sources, he is depicted as a dog. The deity known as Bastet is lion-like, or a woman's head is embodied in the form of a lion's head. In other images, she is depicted with kittens by her side, as she is recognized as the goddess of fertility. In ancient Egypt, people believed in cats and worshiped them. If someone's cat died, the owner mourned the cat and shaved its eyebrows. Among many Turkic peoples, the image of a dog is considered a symbol of courage, nobility, loyalty and faithfulness.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. A dog is one of the domestic animals that have been living side by side with people for several thousand years, guarding the territory, things, and animals belonging to humanity, showing their loyalty, courage, and selflessness. In historical sources, there are different opinions about the faithful dog and its training for human hands. For example, in many stories of Said Ahmad, one of the Uzbek writers, the image of a dog is depicted with special aesthetic coloring and skill. Even in the epigraph of one story, it is mentioned that “*Jannatga kiradigan o'n nafar hayvondan biri bu “Ashobi kahf”ning vafodor itidir*” [8]. In the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, the dog is defined as follows. A four-legged mammal pet kept for household guarding, hunting, and other purposes. *Ko'ppak it, ov iti. Katta temir darvoza ostida cho'zilib yotgan hirsday it boshini ko'tarib irilladi* (A.Qahhor: 1996). Boshsiz odam. Shu hayvonga nisbatlanuvchi haqoratni bildiradi. Azizbek qarshisida qo'l bog'lab turgan darvoza begiga qaradi. - *Nega qarab turasan, darvoza ustiga chiq, kim ekan, u it?* A.Qodiriy. O'tgan kunlar. Xalq tovushi tinimsiz guvullaydi: - *Bu yoqqa chiq, itlar!* (Oybek. Selected works: 18).

One of the most common animal names in Uzbek literature is a dog. There are many zoomorphisms associated with the name of the dog in the literature. Including, - *lekin ustoz hayot vaqtida ipakday muloyim, itday sadoqatli bo'lgan bu bukri savdogar jon taslim qilgan kuni kechasi uning qiziga, eri o'lib tul qolgan qizi Rayhonabonuga tajovuz qilgan, ular shu vajdan qattiq to'qnashgan edi.* (Yakubov, Selection: 1-19). The phrase “loyal as a dog” is used in the above sentence. In this case, it is used in relation to how a dog guards its home, its surroundings, its owner, and its belongings. The zoomorphism presented here serves to strengthen the meaning of the text and to increase its stylistic color.

Here is another zoomorphism related to dogs... - *A'zoyi badani qattiq charchoqdan holdan toygan Martin bu yerda itday ishlab, ijod to'g'risida o'ylash u yoqda tursin, o'zini ham unutilib qo'yadi.* (Language and literature education, 2006: 66). In the excerpts

from the above works of art, the phrase “works here like a dog” is used to describe a hard-working, tireless and very tired person in a brighter and more reliable way. In our daily life, i.e., in our conversational style, the phrase “I’m tired as a dog” is used in the language of tired people who work from morning till night. - *Nega u o’z otam, rahnamomday tuyuladi, nega uni ko’rsam unga qul bo’lgim keladi, etaklarini o’pgim, unga xush yoqish uchun itday hurgim, yaltoqlangim keladi? Nega uni ko’rsam egasini ko’rgan itday ichimda baxtiyorlik, saodat uyg’onadi? (Nazar Eshonqul, The Man Led by the Monkey: 91)*. In this passage, an attempt is made to describe the image of a person who is toady and flatters himself in front of others. That is, the dog is always around its owner and responds with various actions to please him. In our language, the phrase “don’t flatter like a dog” can also be an explanation for the above example.

But similes associated with the name of this animal are not always used in a positive sense. In the excerpts from the following works of art, zoomorphisms associated with dogs served to embody the image of negative people. *Bilardim itday o’lib ketishingni itdan farqing yo’q edi! O’ldir, meni ham o’ldir, qotil! - parrixta, sho’rida Ko’k Tursun o’zini Bo’stonga otdi. - Meni ham itday o’ldir. (Aytmatov, The Day Lasts More Than a Hundred Years: 545). Itday akillab o’tdim! Janнат xola. «Itday akillash» ingiz tagida qanchalik mehr borligini bilardim. (Boboyev, Nameless Stars: 254). Kecha jo’ram qanday dam olyapti ekan, deb xabar olgani kelsam, itday qopib berdinga. Sirkang suv ko’tarmaydigan bo’p qopti o’zi. Odatdagidek, ortiqcha mulozamatsiz osongina yarashishadi. (Eastern Star, 1992: 48).*

In the excerpts from the above works of art, the phrase “dying like a dog” is used for people who are constantly speaking words that come to their mouths, who die neglected and humiliated. That is, the phrase “wanderer dog” is also used for homeless and neglected people.

According to the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language, dog is also used in the sense of insulting this animal [3]. In other words, the word “dog” is used as a derogatory term for people who are incompetent, lazy, greedy, and hypocrite. *For example: Hoy, it! Nechun shariat panohlarini haqorat qilding? G’ofir. Boyota! Men xotinfurushlarni haqorat qildim, xolos! Qozi. Hoy, it fe’l, qadr bilmas! (M.Isroilova, 1981: 80). Mo’min. - Hoy it! Sigaret chekmaysanmi? razvedkachi oyog’i bilan uning iyagidan ko’tardi, - buni qaranglarga! Bu kishim granatamyot bilan jang qiladilar. (Norkobil, Who Wakes the Sun: 208)*. In the above examples, the transfer of meaning is used. That is, the root meaning of the word “dog” includes the meanings of barren, disrespectful and insulting.

Sometimes in literature and in everyday life, the phrase “puppy” is also visible. Puppy: The child of a dog, born of a dog (applies to a young child). *Nuqul itvachcha der emish, astag’firullo, o’z bolasini, o’zi tug’gan bolasini itvachcha desa-ya! A. Qahhor. The lights of Koshchinar.* With this meaning (mainly in relation to young people) it is used for insult. *Shoshmay tur, hali u izzatni bilmagan itvachchani tutib adabini*

bermasam, Madumar otimni boshqa qo’yib yuboraman. The word “puppy” is used in a negative sense in the excerpts from the following works of art. *Xudoning balosi, itvachcha! Maktabda kiming bor? O’liging qola qolsa bo’lmasmidi shu maktabda! - Kennoyim qulog’imni burab ura ketdi, - itvachcha, yetimcha! Bo’rining bolasi o’lganda ham it bo’lmaydi! (Aitmatov, First Teacher:18). Yolg’on aytyapsan, itvachcha! Pora olishni ikki barobar kuchaytirganingdan xabarim bor. Tushgan pullarni shahar tashqarisidagi uyingga berkitib qo’yganingni ham bilaman (Tokhtaboyev, Riding the yellow giant: 290). Sher bo’lsang, kuchingni ko’rsat, itvachcha! G’oyat chaqqonlik ko’rsatib, qattiq zarb bilan Salimning ko’kragiga pichoq urdi. (Oibek, Selected Works of Four Volumes: 2-320).*

The word “puppy” is also usually used in the sense of insulting, derogation, swearing. Often, older people say “puppy” to scold, insult, and touch the ego of younger people. In the fiction literature, there are also expressions related to the name of the dog animal: For example, the phrase “dog sucked” is used to insult, scold, dishallow. - *It emgan Haydarning gapini eshitdingmi, hali? Ha, deydi, shu afandi maktabida o’qib chiqqon bolalar, deydi, ayraplaniga tushub uchar emish, deydi. (Qadiri, Mallavoy in Jirvan, 295)...xudoy haqqi betahorat qiladi, it emganing uzi partiynay ekan-a, xumsa. - Anuv, Xoshim xezalakni taniysanmi. Ana o’sha lapka ko’targan saki bedumingb ham to’rtta go’dagi bilan xotunini qo’yipti, it emgan, endi bir tatarskasiga. (Qadiri, 1993: 18).*

This phrase is used in the sense of insulting, humiliating and cursing. Often, big and rich officials use this sentence in relation to the disrespect and rudeness of their lower castes.

But often among the Turkic peoples, the image of a dog is embodied as a symbol of loyalty, faithfulness and hard work. Because since ancient times, among many Turkic peoples, the dog has been a constant loyal friend and companion in hunting. But on the contrary, in the culture and art of many European nations, it is the opposite. A dog is primarily a domestic animal adapted for guarding, monitoring its territory through its senses. A dog has a highly developed ability to see, hear, smell, and anticipate danger. The proverb “*Tunda balo kezmasa, it akkillamas*” was created taking into account these characteristics of the dog.

Zoomorphisms are selected based on the nationality, lifestyle and culture of the people in the semantic field of each language. In particular, the image of a sheep is often mentioned in works of art. The well-known translator and scientist G. Salomov in his treatise “On the issue of translating proverbs, matals and idioms from Russian to Uzbek” focused on this topic and wrote “...the symbol of evil, pestilence is a snake, a scorpion; the symbol of savagery is a wolf; a symbol of gentleness are a laughing dove (that’s why it is called “carefree like a laughing dove”), a sheep; a symbol of hard work are ants and bees; symbol of size are an elephant, a camel; a symbol of cunning is a fox; a symbol of rudeness is a bear; a symbol of ignorance and recklessness is a donkey, a pig; a symbol of peace is a dove;

a symbol of beauty is a peacock; Nightingale is a symbol of happiness. But in different peoples, objects of analogy may have their own characteristics [1] The scientist also points out that in the works of Homer, the cow is interpreted as a symbol of the beauty of a lover, while a donkey and a fly are embodied as symbols of courage.

In particular, it is embodied in artistic works as a symbol of meekness and calmness. The word "sheep" is used in various figurative meanings for people. In the common language, the names of sheep are still different depending on their gender, age, and color. That is, each of them has its own name in the language. A ram is an unshorn male sheep over two years old. This word has been used in the history of Turkic languages for a long time, and M. Koshgari states that it is an Ugz word used in its chinar and kochbinar forms [2]. Also, in the common language, the term pichma is used for a shorn male sheep, while the term ishshak is used for a two-year-old sheep. In the history of Turkic languages, the term used in the form of qo'zu (lamb) [2] is now used in the form of ship in the common language. *An example of this is that Hazrat Ali, the leader of the saints, said "Doim mening xotirim bo'ri tekkan qo'ydek tarqab sochiladi, men esam cho'pondek, ularni yig'ish bilan ovoraman, ular esa qochish bilan" (Donish, Navodirul-waqoe: 2021: 282). Xuddi bo'yniga arqon solingan qo'ydek ergashganim o'zimga alam qildi. Qo'yvor! - dedim jildni bo'ynimdan olib. (Hoshimov, Sale of life: 1993, 343). ...bo'lgan tog'am bu gal o'zini, negadir, qo'ydek yuvosh tutibdi. — Tavba, dedi Bozorvoy amakim ovqatlanib o'tirgan xotini Lutfi xolamga qarab. (Tokhtabayev, Mungli ko'zlar: 1991, 197). Ho'kiz esa, qassob qo'lida pichoqni ko'rib itoatkorlik bilan bo'ynini cho'zgan qo'ydek, boshini tuproqqa qo'yib, olaygan ko'zlarini podachiga tikdi. (Kholmirzayev, Volumes: 2003, 301).*

The wolf, which is one of the wild animals, has been interpreted as a symbol of strength, bravery and courage among Turkic peoples since ancient times. The wolf was the sacred animal, or totem, of the ancient Turks. Since ancient times, the wolf has been considered as a guide, a giver of wisdom and courage, a symbol of freedom and independence of the Turks. In Chinese sources, the term "wolf" was understood equally with the Turkish khagan, that is, the powerful khagans were assessed as "a person with all the characteristics of a wolf". Shu bo'riday tashlanadi. Ko'rganman-da... O'zi mard odamlar sodda keladi, to'g'rimi? Shu gap-ingiz to'g'ri...(Kholmirzayev, Volumes: 2005, 380). *For example, shofyori hozir oldida bo'lsa bo'riday g'ajib tashlardi. Heh, tavba, kambag'alning orqa tomiri tarang bo'ladi, deb bekorga aytishmaskan-da. (Khazratkulov, Kokkol: 2005, 43). Bir shisha aroq bilan uni yegandan keyin yana bir shisha aroqni yarim qildi va shundan so'ng och bo'riday uvlab-uvlab uyquga ketdi. (Cholpon, Works: 1994, 229).* The names of wild animals in the Uzbek language are familiar to many: lion, tiger, wolf, fox, bear, giraffe, leopard. A lion is a large representative of the feline family. Because they do not know fear, our people call brave young men like lions, and brave and strong young men are described as *sherkelbat* (Lion-shaped). In a figurative sense, it refers

to a person as a lion (in the sense of majesty, hero, wrestler).

- *Balli., sher, xatni qo'lingizdan kim oldi? –Bir chol. (A. Qadiri, Days gone. 2013, 16).* Lions, tigers, leopards, and husbands are here. It is used in the sense of being in a state and movement like a lion. We can also find different interpretations in other sources. *Fig'on qilgan bunda sherlar, Yo'lbars, qoplon, bunda erlar. It is used in the sense of being in a state and movement like a lion. We can also find different interpretations in other sources. Ali Qushchi o'zini bosishga qancha urinmasin, go'yo qafasga tushgan sherday betoqat bo'lib, hibsonada gir aylanar, qorong'ida tur-tinib g'adir - budir devorlarni, temir koplangan og'ir eshikni qayta-qayta paypaslab ko'rardi. (Yakubov, Treasure of Ulugbek: 1978, 203). Oqibat zanjirband etildi sherdek, lek boshin egmadi bo'ysunmas erdek! Diyonat xo'rlandi, bulg'andi iymon, Insof chavaqlandi, bo'g'ildi vijdon. (Boyqabilov, Quiet Khorasan: 1992, 250).*

Today, in many historical works, it is noted that "bugra" means a camel with two scythes [5]. In this regard, Muhammedjanov commented that "bugra" means a saddled camel that carries a heavy load [6]. It is known that "bugra" is the totem of the Yagmo tribe. The Yagmo tribe was a herdsman and had a nomadic way of life. The nomadic life was certainly hard, and it was not easy to drive one's livestock from place to place. The existing political, socio-economic conflicts are also difficult for all the nomadic tribes, until they often change the areas where they live, and sometimes they stay in neglected sandy deserts for a long time. The religious beliefs of these tribes were also formed in such a difficult situation. They often chose this animal as a totem, i.e. the beginning of their ancestors. Therefore, the totem of the Yagmo tribe was also considered "bugra" based on these principles. "Bugra" is clearly a camel. But not every camel became a totem. Because in the above-mentioned conditions of life, the heavy load-carrying camels were of great importance. Among such camels can be included male camels that have been slaughtered. Their load-carrying capacity and level of endurance were also higher than that of ordinary unslaughtered and female camels. As we can see, in this matter A.R. Muhammadjanov's opinions can be considered correct.

In fact, "bugra" is a camel that carries a heavy load, and it is considered the largest of the camels. It was not for nothing that the nomadic herdsman Yagmo tribe chose this powerful animal as their totem. Of course, at that time, the camel was also highly valued as a means of transportation on long, difficult roads. Thus, "bugra" is a saddled camel that carries a heavy load and was considered a totem of the Yagmo tribe, which was later used instead of a title in the name of the Khakans. However, the sources do not say exactly when and why the term "bugra" was used instead of a title in the name of the Khagan.

In the following sentences, a camel is described as person that is going without water for a long time, swallowing when it sees water, drinking in a hurry, and cannot get enough even after drinking so much. *Men ham yutoqqan tuyaday ichaveribman. Bir vaqt qarasam,*

boshqa xonada yotibman. (Kholmirezayev, Volumes: 2005, 276). *Oynisa o'rik shoxiga osiqlik ketmonni olib ariqdan gulzorga suv ochib yubordi, qatqaloq yer namni chanqoq tuyaday simira boshladi.* (H. Ghulam, People of Tashkent: 1975, 125).

Sometimes the phrase “like a drunken camel” is used in the works of art: *Havoning qovog'i soliq, dengiz notinch, katta - katta to'lqinlar mast tuyaday ko'pirib, kemani u yoqdan - bu yoqqa uloqtirar edi.* (Kadyrov, *Pass of Generations: 1994, 187*). Mast tuyaday o'kirgan Davronning endi hech narsadan qaytmasligini sezadi. O'lim xavfidan o'zini yo'qotib qo'yadi va qo'rqib orqaga tisariladi. (Kadyrov, *Meros: 1975, 327*).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS. It can be concluded from the above-mentioned points that we can find many zoomorphisms related to the name of the animal in the works of art. There are especially many zoomorphisms related to the name of a dog. Each animal acquires a different color from the point of view of the situation, that is, sometimes it is positive, and sometimes it is negative. In particular, dog-related zoomorphisms are interpreted more in a positive way. But most of the related phraseology is distinguished by having a negative connotation. It can be said separately that the image of a dog in folklore serves to illuminate almost all aspects of the daily life of the Uzbek people.

Regardless of the nationality and language of the people they are used, they create positive skills such as enriching the folk art, being able to evaluate positive and negative situations in people, understanding the happenings and the right approach to every work. If we observe the use of animal names in folklore, we can see that each animal name has its own seminal develop-

ment. Because their manifestation in speech is different, and each zoonym acquires a figurative meaning according to its different characteristics, natural living conditions, and people's attitude.

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